

Defining the Trigonometric Chart

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Abstract:- It's impossible that so many researchers and scientists have left this behind and studying it. I think its incorrect proposed wrong chart.

I. INTRODUCTION

How can 3 be involved in this chart if we are taking 1 and 2 as parameters of a triangle with one right angle, neither can we take their roots as parameter as distances are generally and widely natural numbers .The table is absurd and incorrect.

Here lets define and correct them by basic right angled triangle.

Fig 1 Basic Right Angled Triangle.

Let theta = z

Sin z = (opposite side)/(longest side)
Cos z = (adjacent side)/(longest side)
Tan z = (opposite side)/(adjacent side)

Sin 90° = x/a
Cos 90° = b/a
Tan 90° = x/b or x/a

Here x is opposite side to angle 90°
And a is longer side
And b is adjacent shortest side

Fig 2 Angle 90°

Here, $\theta = z = 30^\circ$

Fig 3 Angle 30°

Here, $\theta = z = 60^\circ$

Fig 4 Angel 60°

Fig 5 Angle 180°

Here $\theta = z = 180^\circ$

Here, $\sin 180^\circ = 8/8$ or $9/9$ or $7/7$
Same for cosine and tangent of angle 180°

$\theta = z = 270^\circ$

Fig 6 Angle 270⁰

{Yet to be find at 270⁰}

Cosine of any angle =adjacent side /longest side

Tangent of any angle=opposite side/adjacent side

(Condition is it should be right angled triangle)

I have arrived at following table at considering the formulas

Sine of any angle =opposite side / longest side

Table 1 Values of Sine , Cosine , Tangent at Different Angles

trigonometric functions	Degrees				
	0	30	60	90	180
sin z	0	3/5	4/5	1	1
cos z	4/5	4/5	3/5	4/5 or 3/5	1
tan z	0	3/4 or 3/5	4/3 or 4/5	5/4 or 5/3	1

II. CONCLUSION

Every value is defined in sin ,cos ,tan tables

REFERENCES

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- [3.] Book higher engineering mathematics by B S Grewal
- [4.] Information from eddie woo online classes
- [5.] NCERT BOOKS of classes 6 to 12
- [6.] I studied them by heart they are knowledge Which is the curriculum of Central board of secondary education in Delhi and other parts of India.

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